

Station: CO₂ Usage

≙ 6 kg CO₂eq per year

Select your scenario!

from **A** (CO₂ -low)
to **D** (CO₂ -high)

Guiding questions:

The guiding questions will help you to gradually understand the differences between the scenarios and maintain an overview.

No
blocks

A

B

C

D

		No blocks			
		A	B	C	D
I spend ... per day on social media.		< 10 min	< 1 h	< 3 h	≥ 3h
I prefer to visit ... social media sites [A].		none	WhatsApp / Twitch / X (Twitter)	Facebook / Snapchat / Pinterest	Instagram / Reddit / TikTok / YouTube
I post ... on social media.		... just a few highlights per year	... every month	... every week	... (almost) daily
In everyday life, I use Wi-Fi.	... Wi-Fi, except for smaller tasks(emails ...).	... sometimes Wi-Fi, sometimes mobile data.	... mostly mobile data.
I listen to ... hours of audio content per day in real time (streaming) [B].		< 2 h	2-7 h	7-15 h	> 15 h
I watch ... videos per day in real time (streaming) [B].		... none	< 1 h	1-2 h	> 2 h
I watch videos in real time (streaming) in ... quality [B].		SD (480p) or less	HD (720p)	Full-HD (1080p)	4k
I play ... video games on my smartphone every day.		... none	1-4 h	> 4 h	\
I save my data locally and sort it regularly.	... local on my device.	... in the cloud.	... locally and in the cloud.
I send and receive ... text messages and emails per day		< 70	70-300	> 300	\
I use search engines ... times a day.		< 25	25-149	150-300	> 300
I use generative AI or digital assistants (Siri, ...) ... times a day.		< 1	1-7	8-15	> 15

[A] If none or more the one of the above options apply, please select option C (3 blocks).

[B] Streaming involves playing audio and video content in real time, meaning that it does not need to be downloaded previously (Cloudflare. (n.d.). Was ist Streaming? | Wie Streaming von Videos funktioniert. Retrieved March 30, 2025, from <https://www.cloudflare.com/de-de/learning/video/what-is-streaming/>).